

Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions: Library Research and Bibliometrics VOSviewer

Fitri Khoirotul Ummah, Eka Wahyu Hestya Budianto, Nindi Dwi Tetria Dewi

Universitas Islam Negeri Maulana Malik Ibrahim Malang, Indonesia
wahyu.ala@uin-malang.ac.id

Abstract

This research aims to map research topics surrounding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions using a qualitative approach, which is in the nature of a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key “DSN-MUI Fatwa” within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions based on the journals that have been collected. The research results showed that there were 40 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Keywords: Fatwa; National Sharia Council (DSN); Indonesian Ulama Council (MUI); Bibliometrics; VOSviewer; Library Research; Islamic Financial Institutions

Introduction

The development of science and technology has a close relationship with development demands that affect all aspects of life, including the financial sector. Apart from providing many conveniences, this technology also creates various new problems and behaviors that may not have been known or even thought of before (Amin, 2015).

Fatwa is the result of Islamic law that has existed since the time of the prophet and continues to develop today. Fatwas issued by Islamic scholars and fatwa bodies contained in the book of fiqh are part of causal ijtihad because they are answers to questions asked by fatwa applicants (Khaeruman, 2010). Therefore, fatwa is one solution to solve the problems that occur in this modern era (Afrelian & Furqon, 2019).

The Indonesian Ulema Council (MUI) is an advisory forum for Islamic scholars, *zu'ama'*, and intellectuals in Indonesia as well as the best institution that meets the requirements to answer and resolve socio-religious issues in Indonesia. MUI also has the trust of the community and government. MUI was

founded on July 26 1975, the result of meetings or discussions between researchers, ulama, and zu'ama' from all over the archipelago, including 26 regions in Indonesia at that time (Habibaty, 2017). Basically, the MUI's role is to issue fatwas and provide advice to the government on religious and social issues, as well as providing advice to Muslims in general about right and wrong. The MUI issues fatwas based on requests or questions from individuals, community organizations, the government, or the MUI itself which the MUI deems necessary to issue (Mudzhar, 2012).

In the financial sector, the MUI formed the National Sharia Council (DSN) as a working body specifically tasked with handling the operations of Islamic Financial Institutions (LKS) as well as issues related to Islamic finance. This is stated in MUI management decision no. kep-754/MUI/II/1999 dated 10 February 1999. The task and role of DSN-MUI is to issue sharia financing fatwas and serve as guidelines for organizers and regulators. Currently, DSN-MUI has issued 81 fatwas. However, DSN-MUI itself is not aware of the impact of fatwa law on positive law when used as an operational basis for LKS. Nevertheless, many important DSN MUI fatwas are outlined in various laws and regulations, especially those that apply in the field of Islamic finance for Islamic financial institutions. (Afrelian & Furqon, 2019).

Scientific publications regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa increase every year. Based on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garuda), 94 journals were published between 2011 and 2022. This proves that research developments surrounding the DSN-MUI Fatwa are of great interest to researchers.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions using library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the gaps in research on this topic.

Literature Review

Fatwa is one of the centers of Islamic law that provides answers and solutions related to legal problems faced by society. The existence of fatwas is a fundamental part of sharia economics that needs to be maintained or improved, and is also a sign of the progress of sharia economics in Indonesia. The newest fatwa in sharia economics is *maliyah fiqh muamalah* (economic jurisprudence) or development methods. Indonesia is regulated by the Sharia Economic Fatwa Agency (DSN-MUI). This fatwa issued by the MUI fatwa commission is a complete and comprehensive guide for Muslims in Indonesia. The DSN fatwa is mandatory for LKS, but also applies to people associated with LKS in Indonesia (Nurhayati et al., 2018).

Islamic Financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and

investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Islamic Financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of Islamic Financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Islamic Financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, Islamic Financial inclusion also supports the development of the Islamic Financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022) .

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including

social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022) .

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The object of the research is the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles regarding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keywords " National Sharia Board " and " National Sharia Board" for the entire year period (2011 -2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research.

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa in Islamic Financial Institutions

The results of scientific publication research regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa in Islamic Financial Institutions during the period 2011 to 2021 show fluctuations or ups and downs from year to year, especially in the last four years. In 2019, there were 19 published articles, while in 2020 there were 13 published articles.

Table 1. Scientific publication data regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa by year period

Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Publication Articles
2011	1	2015	2	2019	19
2012	3	2016	13	2020	13
2013	2	2017	11	2021	12
2014	1	2018	10	2022	7
Total 94					

Source: Processed Data, Microsoft Excel 2019

Table 2 shows the four affiliates or institutions that publish the most research articles regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa in Islamic Financial Institutions. The Sharia Economic Law Journal is the journal publishing institution that publishes the most research results regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa, namely 7 articles.

Table 2. Affiliates/institutions publishing journals regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
Al-Manahij: Journal of Islamic Law Studies, Al-Muamalat: Journal of Sharia Economics, A mwaluna (Journal of Sharia Economics and Finance), Salam: Journal of Sharia Social and Cultural Affairs	2
At-Taradhi Journal of Economic Studies	4
Journal of Sharia Economic Law	7
Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Tadayun: Journal of Sharia Economic Law	3
(Budianto, 2022) (Budianto, 2022) (Budianto & Dewi, 2022) (Rohimah et al., 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Dewi et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Rohmandika et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Emiliani et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto, 2023) (Budianto, Saputra, et al., 2023) (Gozali et al., 2023) (Rofika et al., 2023) (Budianto, Dewi, et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Zahro et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Rahmawati et al., 2023) (Shalsabila et al., 2023) (Fitriawati et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023) (Febrian & Budianto, 2023) (Rohmah et al., 2023) (Budianto & Dewi, 2023)	

Source: Processed Data, Microsoft Excel 2019

Several researchers have the same productivity value, namely 2 journal articles, namely: Panji Adam Agus (Islamic University of Bandung), Akhmad Faozan (IAIN Purwokerto), Muhammad Rifqi Hidayat (UIN Antasari), Parman Komarudin (Islamic University of Kalimantan Muhammad Arsyad Al-Banjari), and Fitriyani Zein (UIN Syarif Hidayatullah Jakarta).

Bibliometric Mapping of Research Regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa on Islamic Financial Institutions

Research articles from searches on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported in RIS (Research Information Systems) format, input and analyzed with VOSviewer. The results are as follows:

Figure 1. Depiction of the growth map relationship surrounding the DSN-MUI Fatwa on Islamic Financial Institutions

- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 3 topics, namely: dsn mui number, istishna, legal basis.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the DSN-MUI Fatwa

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 40 topics related to the DSN-MUI Fatwa, namely:

First, a fatwa on the Islamic legal aspects of sharia banking.

Second, economic jurisprudence legislation and sharia banking compliance with fatwas.

Third, the role of fatwa in: (1) Development of sharia banking business. (2) Development of Islamic economic law products. (3) Sharia compliance.

Fourth, the relationship between DSN-MUI and: (1) Majma Fiqh Organization of the Islamic Conference/OIC (application of fatwa sanctions clauses in contracts). (2) Hisbah supervisory institution. (3) Sharia Supervisory Board. (4) Sharia Banking Committee. (5) Financial Services Authority/OJK. (6) Indonesian Ulema Council

Fifth, application of fatwa to Rahn contracts: (1) Fatwa No. 92/DSN-MUI/IV/2014 concerning financing accompanied by Rahn. (2) Fatwa no. 68/DSN-MUI/III/2008: obstacles to debt and receivable agreements with guarantees from Rahn Tasjily. (3) Fatwa no. 25/DSN-MUI/III/2002 concerning the appropriateness of carrying out auctions for problematic Rahn collateral and the responsibility of sharia/ murtahin pawnshops in the event that the pawned object is damaged/lost. (4) Fatwa no. 28/DSN-MUI/III/2002 concerning gold pawning products.

Sixth, implementation of fatwa no. 60 of 2000 concerning the Istishna' agreement.

Seventh, application of fatwa to Murabahah contracts: (1) Fines. (2) The style of the school of thought used. (3) Sharia banking. (4) Fatwa no. 4, 17, 43, 111. (5) Gold financing.

Eighth, transformation of fatwa into positive law and legal maxim jurisprudence.

Ninth, implementation of fatwa no. 121/DSN-MUI/II/2018 concerning multi-benefit financing.

Tenth, application of fatwa to sharia insurance: (1) Tabarru' agreement.

Eleventh, application of the fatwa on non-cash gold buying and selling.

Twelfth, application of fatwa to Mudharabah contracts: (1) Mudharabah Muthlaqah in Bank Muamalat Indonesia savings products. (2) Fatwa no. 7/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning Mudharabah financing. (3) School style. (4) Guarantee. (5) Fatwa no. 03/DSN-MUI/IV/2000 concerning Mudharabah Deposits.

Thirteenth, the mechanism for determining fatwa.

Fourteenth, application of fatwa on contract conversions for non-prospective customers.

Fifteenth, application of fatwa to Wakalah contracts in sharia financing companies.

Sixteenth, application of fatwa to Hawalah contracts in sharia financing companies.

Seventeenth, application of fatwa to Kafalah contracts: (1) Sharia financing companies. (2) No. 11/DSN-MUI/IV/2000.

Eighteenth, application of fatwa to multi-contracts.

Nineteenth, application of fatwa to the concept of wa'ad.

Twentieth, application of fatwa to Musyarakah contracts: (1) School style.
Twenty-first, application of fatwa to sharia economic dispute resolution clauses.

Twenty-second, application of fatwa on sharia securities trading on the Indonesia Stock Exchange/IDX.

Twenty-third, implementation of fatwa no. 75/DSN-MUI/VII/2009 concerning sharia-level direct sales at Tiens Syariah.

Twenty-fourth, the dynamics of fatwas from classical to contemporary.

Twenty-fifth, application of fatwa on sharia electronic money: (1) Flazz BCA. (2) Go-Pay. (3) Grab-Pay.

Twenty-sixth, implementation of fatwa no. 108/DSN-MUI/X/2016: (1) Sharia tourism. (2) The role of the Sharia Supervisory Board/DPS in developing sharia tourism.

Twenty-seventh, implementation of fatwa no. 80/DSN-MUI/III/2011 concerning sharia online trading system.

Twenty-eighth, the application of the fatwa on the fine of bai' bitsaman ajil.

Twenty-ninth, application of fatwa to the Ijarah Multijasa contract.

Thirtieth, application of fatwa on Qardh contracts: (1) Fatwa No. 19/DSN-MUI/IV/2001.

Thirty-first, implementation of fatwa no. 119/DSN-MUI/II/2018 concerning ultra-micro financing in accordance with regulation no. 95/PMK.05/2018.

Thirty-second, implementation of fatwa no. 40/DSN-MUI/X/2003 concerning Sharia Capital Markets.

Thirty-third, hadith study regarding the business results distribution system in Islamic Financial Institutions/LKS.

Thirty-fourth, application of fatwa to sharia hedging transactions in commodity futures markets.

Thirty-fifth, implementation of fatwa on Financial Technology compliance No. 117.

Thirty-sixth, implementation of fatwa no. 98/DSN-MUI/XII/2015 concerning guidelines for implementing sharia social health security.

Thirty-seventh, application of fatwa on sharia cards.

Thirty-eighth, implementation of fatwa no. 77/DSN-MUI/V/2010 concerning gold installments.

Thirty-ninth, implementation of fatwa no. 17/DSN-MUI/IX/2000 concerning fines on Islamic Financial Institutions.

Fortieth, National Sharia Council/DSN certification.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 40 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding the Fatwa of the National Sharia Council of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN-MUI) on Islamic Financial Institutions.

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